

Studies on the effect of substituents on the solvational behavior of 2-, 3- and 4-benzoic acids and their anions in ethanol + water mixtures from conductometric and solubility measurements[†]

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The solvational behaviour of 2-, 3- and 4-substituted-chloro, -bromo, -iodo and -nitrobenzoic acids were examined from the solubility of the acids and the dissociation constants for the reaction,

determined conductometrically using Fuoss-Kraus method in ethanol + water mixtures (0–87 wt % of ethanol).

The solubility values increase with the increase in hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures and the changes depend both on the hydrophobic character and the dielectric constants of the solvent media. The sequence of the solubilities of the substituted acids are in the order : 2-compounds > 3-compounds > 4-compounds and $-\text{NO}_2 > -\text{Cl} > -\text{Br} > -\text{I}$. The Λ_0 -values of the substituted benzoic acids are almost similar but the order is Λ_0 (*ortho*) > Λ_0 (*meta*) > Λ_0 (*para*). Λ_0 -values of the nitrobenzoic acids are lower but the order is reversed.

The Gibbs energies of transfer of anions were determined from the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{dissn.}) = \Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-) - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})$$

using the previously determined values of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$. The $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ values are found to be increasingly positive in aquo-organic mixtures and $\Delta G_t^0(\text{A}^-)$ values are usually in the order : 2-compounds > 3-compounds > 4-compounds. Nitrobenzoates differ from halobenzoates in their solvational behavior.

The results are discussed in the light of change in the solute-solvent interactions of the substituted acids due to the change in dipole moments, polarizability, hydrogen-bonding and dispersion interactions. The effects of substitution on the interaction energies of anions were determined. Substituents change the interaction energies of neutral acids and their anions in a different way.

The importance of ion-solvent interactions has attracted wide attention and is the subjectmatter of discussion^{1–5}. It is known that the solvation of ions in the gas phase can be studied experimentally or in spite of limitations can be evaluated theoretically⁶. However, the problem is extremely complicated in the bulk solvents where thermodynamic evaluation of ion-solvation is not possible. The values of ion-solvation energies can be obtained by splitting the experimental thermodynamic data of electrolytes (like Gibbs energy changes, enthalpy changes etc.) obtained from different experimental techniques using extrathermodynamic assumptions. The results can be utilised to test the various theories of ion-solvation using suitable models or using statistical mechanical concepts.

Ion-solvent interaction has been assumed to be the controlling forces in dilute solutions where ion-ion interactions can be considered to be small. Single ion Gibbs

energy changes or enthalpy changes can be regarded to be the quantitative measures of ion-solvent interactions.

In spite of limitations, data are available on ionic hydration but most of the data relate to inorganic ions¹. But a large number of data exist for the Gibbs energies of transfer of ions, i.e. ΔG_t^0 (i) from water to different non-aqueous solvents or mixed solvents¹. The values are mostly limited to inorganic ions though few data exist for organic ions also^{7–10}. Most of the reactions of biological and medicinal interest occur in solution. Many of the medicinal compounds known as drugs are amphipathic in nature consisting of inorganic and organic ions but most of the organic solvents are abiologic in nature though biologic media consist of water and lipids. Naturally, the knowledge of ion-solvent interactions of organic ions may be useful to understand the mechanisms of drug actions. Moreover, since most of the organic medicinal compounds of interest are organic acids

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

or bases, solvents exert enormous influence on the dissociation processes and kinetics of different reactions. Single ion values are particularly useful for elucidating the mechanisms of reactions in organic solvents¹¹.

These considerations led us to undertake extensive studies on solubility and dissociation processes of organic compounds of different charge types in aquo-organic mixtures^{7-10, 12-16}. Studies on the dissociation constants of acids and bases in non-aqueous solvents have been made by Bates^{17,18}, Reynauds¹⁹ and others²⁰⁻²⁶. Niazi *et al.*²⁷ made conductometric studies of benzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures. However, most of these studies do not relate to the determination of solubility and single ion values.

We present in this communication the conductometric studies on the dissociation constants of 2-, 3- and 4-substituted chloro-, bromo-, iodo- and nitro-substituted benzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures (0-87 wt% of ethanol). The results have been coupled with solubility data to determine Gibbs energies of transfer of organic anions. The results are likely to throw insight on the effect of solvents and substituents on the solubility, dissociation, conductance and ion-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction,

(HA = substituted benzoic acid) can be written as

$$K = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{A}^-}}{C_{\text{HA}}} \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{A}^-}}{\gamma_{\text{HA}}} \quad (2)$$

where γ represents the respective activity coefficients. In dilute solutions, γ_{HA} can be reasonably assumed to be unity.

The initial values of A_0 (HBz)_{subs} and K were obtained from the plot of AC against $1/A$ of the solutions of HA utilising the equation,

$$AC = -KA_0 + KA_0^2/1/A \quad (3)$$

The accuracy of the method is known to be limited. Therefore, the method of computation suggested by Fuoss and Kraus^{28,29} was utilised. The equation is

$$\frac{F(Z)}{A} = \frac{1}{KA_0^2} \frac{AC\gamma_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{A_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } Z = \frac{(\theta A_0 + \sigma)\sqrt{(AC)}}{A_0^{3/2}} \quad (5)$$

The values of the Onsager constants σ and θ ,

$$\sigma = \frac{82.4}{(\epsilon T)^{1/2} \eta} \text{ and } \theta = \frac{8.20 \times 10^3}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \quad (6)$$

were calculated utilising η (viscosity)¹⁰ and dielectric constants ϵ (with suitable interpolations where necessary) values of the binary mixtures from the literature²⁵. $F(Z)$ values were obtained from literature²⁸. γ_{\pm} values in dilute solution ($\approx 10^{-3} M$) were calculated using Debye-Hückel limiting law,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\alpha C} \quad (7)$$

with appropriate values of A and $\alpha = A/A_0$ [$A = 1.823 \times 10^6 Z_+^2 / (\epsilon T)^{3/2}$].

The physical parameters are presented in Table 1. The slopes and the intercepts from the plot of $F(Z)/A$ against $AC\gamma_{\pm}^2/F(Z)$ were calculated using the method of least-squares. The values of the slopes ($1/KA_0^2$) were accepted only when the values of the regression coefficients were better than 0.995. A_0 -values obtained from the intercepts involve

Table 1. Physical properties of the EtOH + H₂O mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of EtOH	Density ρ_0 g cm ⁻³	Viscosity η_0 c _p	Dielec. const. ϵ	Mol. wt. of the assorted solvent (M_s)	Mol. vol. $V^0 = M_s/\rho_0$	A
0.0	0.9971	0.890	78.740	18.02	18.07	0.5090
8.0	0.9838	1.420	74.074	18.94	19.25	0.5552
16.4	0.9722	1.695	70.423	20.01	20.59	0.6130
25.3	0.9628	1.959	65.259	21.29	22.12	0.6939
34.4	0.9448	2.215	58.480	22.78	24.12	0.7912
44.0	0.9245	2.345	52.632	24.60	26.61	0.9270
54.1	0.9035	2.276	46.729	26.85	29.72	1.133
64.7	0.8779	2.115	40.984	29.71	33.84	1.348
76.0	0.8503	1.843	34.843	33.51	39.41	1.707
87.6	0.8211	1.498	29.674	38.57	46.57	2.179

long extrapolations. Naturally, the accuracy of such values may be questioned. The limitations were avoided by determining A_0 -values of weak acids using Kohlrausch's additivity rules,

$$A_0(\text{HA}) = A_0(\text{HClO}_4) + A_0(\text{KA}) - A_0(\text{KClO}_4) \quad (8)$$

$A_0(\text{HClO}_4)$ and $A_0(\text{KClO}_4)$ were taken from the data previously determined^{12,14}. The solubility, pK-values and A_0 -values of the substituted acids are given in Tables 2–4.

In the determination of solubility of benzoic acids in aqueous and aquo-alcoholic binary mixtures, the saturated solutions of the acids in the respective solvent systems are in equilibrium with the respective solid acids, their Gibbs energies are also equal². Thus

$$\Delta G_A^0 = {}_w\bar{G}_{\text{HA}}^0 + RT \ln {}_w a_A(\text{satd}) = {}_s\bar{G}_{\text{HA}}^0 + RT \ln {}_s a_{\text{HA}}(\text{satd}) \quad (9)$$

Thus, Gibbs energies of transfer of neutral acid from refer-

ence solvent water to mixed solvents is

$$\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA}) = {}_s\bar{G}_{\text{HA}}^0 - {}_w\bar{G}_{\text{HA}}^0 = -2.303 RT \log \frac{{}_s a_{\text{HA}}(\text{satd})}{{}_w a_{\text{HA}}(\text{satd})} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{or, } \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA}) = -2.303 RT \log {}_m \gamma_{\text{HA}} \approx -2.303 RT \log \frac{C_s}{C_w} \quad (11)$$

where ${}_m \gamma_{\text{HA}}$ represent the 'medium effect' for HA. Activity coefficients of benzoic acids should be unity in the respective solvent systems (by convention). C_s and C_w are the molar concentrations of respective acid in aqueous and aquo-alcoholic mixtures. However, benzoic acids are assumed not to form hydrate or solvates in solution. Benzoic acids are known to dissociate slightly in solutions particularly in water-rich mixtures. Proper corrections for the dissociation of acids were made.

Table 2. Solubilities (mol dm⁻³) of substituted-benzoic acids in EtOH + H₂O mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of + EtOH	Chlorobenzoic acids			Bromobenzoic acids			Iodobenzoic acids			Nitrobenzoic acids		
	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-
0.0	0.0210 (0.0208)	0.00408 (0.0041)	0.0008 (0.000797)	0.00905	0.00202	0.0003	0.000785	0.00175	0.0002	0.0334 (0.033395)	0.153 (0.015235)	0.002525 (0.002516)
8.0	0.0282	0.0048	0.0011	0.01335	0.00254	0.0004	0.01193	0.0022	0.0003 [†]	0.0421	0.0225	0.003050
16.4	0.0440	0.0073	0.0015	0.01979	0.00456	0.0007	0.01761	0.0043	0.0005	0.0482	0.0410	0.004975
25.3	0.0525	0.0152	0.0028	0.02445	0.00919	0.0013	0.0221	0.0082	0.0009	0.0581	0.0492	0.007425
34.4	0.0945	0.0628	0.0061	0.04727	0.0349	0.0036	0.0385	0.0322	0.0014	0.0627	0.0534	0.008450
44.0	0.1885	0.1350	0.0125	0.09696	0.0805	0.0095	0.0870	0.0729	0.0031	0.1942	0.1787	0.009075
54.1	0.3770	0.2872	0.0190	0.1940	0.1656	0.0207	0.1740	0.1506	0.0081	0.5485	0.4365	0.009975
64.7	0.4975	0.3978	0.0395	0.2633	0.2460	0.0363	0.2363	0.2323	0.0161	0.8432	0.8141	0.011025
76.0	0.6385	0.4795	0.0758	0.3449	0.3053	0.0600	0.3091	0.2907	0.0298	1.1082	1.0892	0.022575
87.6	0.9270	0.5195	0.1516	0.4938	0.3241	0.0883	0.4325	0.3088	0.0741	1.4821	1.4635	0.034475

Table 3. pK values of substituted-benzoic acids in EtOH + H₂O mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of + EtOH	Chlorobenzoic acids			Bromobenzoic acids			Iodobenzoic acids			Nitrobenzoic acids		
	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-
0.0	2.94 (2.94)	3.84 (3.83)	3.98 (3.98)	2.85 (2.85)	3.81 (3.81)	3.98 (3.96)	2.96 (2.96)	3.85 (3.85)	3.99 (4.00)	2.17 (2.17)	3.49 (3.49)	3.43 (3.43)
8.0	3.10	3.96	4.23	3.01	3.90	4.16	3.12	3.97	4.12	2.51	3.70	3.52
16.4	3.37	4.18	4.44	3.27	4.12	4.37	3.40	4.20	4.30	2.72	3.86	3.73
25.3	3.65	4.40	4.65	3.53	4.31	4.56	3.70	4.41	4.51	3.09	4.10	3.84
34.4	3.88	4.72	4.81	3.75	4.64	4.89	3.91	4.72	4.82	3.41	4.28	4.01
44.0	4.10	4.92	5.05	3.95	4.85	5.02	4.12	4.94	5.05	3.80	4.61	4.29
54.1	4.25	5.20	5.27	4.12	5.20	5.35	4.28	5.22	5.38	4.11	4.85	4.41
64.7	4.39	5.45	5.53	4.27	5.45	5.60	4.41	5.46	5.62	4.49	5.12	4.52
76.0	4.55	5.71	5.79	4.42	5.75	5.88	4.57	5.72	5.91	4.72	5.67	4.88
87.6	4.88	5.82	5.99	4.75	5.95	6.12	4.91	5.84	6.15	5.01	6.26	5.24

Table 4. Equivalent conductances ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ equiv}^{-1}$) of substituted-benzoic acids in EtOH + H₂O mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of EtOH	HClO ₄	KClO ₄	Chlorobenzoic acids						Bromobenzoic acids					
			Potassium salts			Acids			Potassium salts			Acids		
			2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-
0.0	416.6	140.4	119.0	115.6	108.0	395.2	391.8	384.2	119.4	115.8	108.4	395.6	392.0	384.6
8.0	372.0	116.9	94.1	93.0	92.1	349.2	349.2	347.2	94.5	93.3	92.5	349.6	348.4	347.6
16.4	301.5	95.6	81.6	81.0	77.6	288.1	288.1	284.1	82.7	81.3	77.9	289.2	287.8	284.4
25.3	250.0	78.5	68.1	65.7	60.6	239.6	239.6	232.1	68.6	66.1	60.7	240.1	237.6	232.2
34.4	196.0	66.0	55.5	52.4	46.1	185.5	185.5	176.1	56.1	52.8	51.2	186.1	182.8	181.2
44.0	172.6	58.2	42.3	38.2	36.2	156.7	156.7	150.0	42.8	38.8	37.1	157.2	153.2	151.5
54.1	142.0	52.0	40.2	35.8	29.8	130.2	130.2	119.8	40.8	36.2	30.4	130.8	126.2	120.2
64.7	118.0	49.5	34.4	31.6	28.9	102.9	102.9	97.4	34.7	32.1	29.7	103.2	106.6	98.2
76.0	108.0	48.6	32.9	28.6	25.5	92.3	92.3	84.9	33.4	29.0	25.7	92.8	88.4	85.1
87.6	92.0	48.0	30.5	28.1	25.2	74.5	74.1	69.2	31.0	28.5	25.5	75.0	72.5	69.5
			Chlorobenzoic acids						Bromobenzoic acids					
			Potassium salts			Acids			Potassium salts			Acids		
			2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-
0.0	416.6	140.4	119.5	115.9	109.0	395.7	392.1	385.2	89.7	102.2	104.9	365.9	378.4	381.1
8.0	772.0	116.9	94.7	93.7	92.7	349.8	348.8	347.8	68.5	90.2	91.7	323.6	345.3	346.8
16.4	301.5	95.6	82.9	81.5	78.4	289.4	288.0	284.9	57.4	69.2	70.2	263.9	275.7	276.7
25.3	250.0	78.5	68.7	66.6	60.9	240.2	238.1	232.4	43.2	57.6	61.1	214.7	229.1	232.6
34.4	196.0	66.0	56.9	53.0	51.4	186.4	183.0	181.4	38.7	43.4	45.6	168.7	173.4	175.6
44.0	172.6	58.2	43.0	39.1	37.6	157.4	153.5	152.0	33.9	39.0	39.6	148.3	153.4	154.0
54.1	142.0	52.0	41.0	36.4	32.5	131.7	126.4	122.5	31.3	33.7	36.4	121.3	123.7	126.4
64.7	118.0	49.5	35.3	32.4	29.9	103.8	100.9	98.4	30.2	31.6	34.3	98.7	100.1	102.8
76.0	108.0	48.6	33.6	29.4	26.2	93.0	88.8	85.7	28.5	30.2	31.9	87.9	89.6	91.3
87.6	92.0	48.0	31.2	28.7	26.0	75.2	72.7	70.0	27.9	28.5	30.7	71.9	72.5	74.7

Similarly, the transfer Gibbs energies for the dissociation reaction (1) from the reference solvent water to aquo-ethanolic solvents can be written as

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_s^0(1) - \Delta G_w^0(1) - 2.303 RT \log \frac{m\gamma_{H^+} \cdot m\gamma_{A^-}}{m\gamma_{HA}} \quad (12)$$

here $m\gamma_i$ represents the medium effect of the respective species. The expression is the measure of the differences between solute-solvent interactions (of the species involved) in the two ideal reference states with the ion-ion or solute-solute interactions eliminated². The values of $\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})$ and $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ of the benzoic acids can be calculated from Tables 2 and 3.

The solubilities of substituted-benzoic acids at 298 K in ethanol + water mixtures are presented in Table 2. The errors in the solubility measurements are within 0.2 to 0.5% (at higher percentages). The sequence of solubilities of the substituted acids is in the order : 2-compounds (*ortho*) > 3-

compounds (*meta*) > 4-compounds (*para*) and NO₂ > Cl > Br > I. The solubilities of the substituted acids increase with the increase in the hydrophobic character of the aquo-organic solvents. The variations of the solubilities of the substituted benzoic acids in different binary mixtures result from the differences in the cohesive forces of the like solute molecules and solute-solvent interactions of various types³⁰.

The effect of substitution in benzoic acids and the variation of solvent effect can be understood from the plots of $\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$ [transfer of neutral acids from water to aquo-organic mixtures] against wt% of organic co-solvent (Fig. 1), where $\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$ represents

$$\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut}) = \delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{Substituted acid}) - \delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{benzoic acid}) \quad (13)$$

The variation of $\delta\Delta G_t^0$ with solvent composition (Fig. 1) shows that the behaviour of 2-, 3- and 4-compounds are conspicuously different. In spite of differences, Cl, Br and I compounds behave in a similar fashion but nitro compounds behave in a different way.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut}) [= \Delta G_t^0(\text{S.A.})_{\text{neut}} - \Delta G_t^0(\text{A.})_{\text{neut}}]$ of substituted-benzoic acids vs wt% of EtOH.

The substituents change the dipole moments, polarizability of the solutes leading to the variations in dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, ion-quadrupole and dispersion interactions, hydrogen bonding which can be expected to be the greatest in nitrobenzoic acids. However, contribution of the individual components cannot be determined. The fluctuations in $\delta\Delta G_t^0(\text{neut})$ may arise due to dissociation of the substituted acids to different extents and change in solute-solvent interactions. The pK -values of substituted acids are given in Table 3. The accuracy of pK -values ranges from ± 0.01 pK unit in water to ± 0.04 pK -units in higher percentage of organic co-solvents. The pK -values in water agree well with literature values³¹ (in parenthesis).

Λ_0 -values of substituted benzoic acids, determined by us using Kohlrausch's additivity rules, show marginal changes in the Λ_0 -values of acids (Table 4) and as expected Λ_0 -values decrease with increase in organic co-solvent. Unlike Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and NO_2^- ions in electrolytes, the ions in different substituted benzoic acids are inert. Conductivity values of benzoate and substituted benzoates should be almost similar. Thus, only slight variations in Λ_0 -values of the substituted acids are expected due to inductive effect of the substituents. The Λ_0 - values of chloro, bromo and iodo compounds are almost similar and the order usually is $\Lambda_0(\text{ortho})$

$> \Lambda_0(\text{meta}) > \Lambda_0(\text{para})$. Λ_0 -values of the nitrobenzoic acids are lower but the order is reversed.

The dissociation constants of benzoic acid and nitrobenzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures were determined conductometrically by Niazi *et al.*²⁷. The experimental data had been analysed with Lea and Wheaton conductance equation³² which is akin to Fuoss equation³³. Niazi *et al.* did not claim any improvement in pK -values. The determination of Λ_0 -values reported by Niazi *et al.* involves long extrapolations. Even Niazi *et al.* pointed out that in case of benzoic acid for 60 and 70% ethanol + water mixtures, extrapolations to zero concentration were impossible. Λ_0 -values reported by Niazi *et al.* are anomalous and erratic as will be apparent from the comparison of Λ_0 -values of the acids (Table 5).

Table 5. Λ_0 -values of benzoic acids

Wt.% of + EtOH	Benzoic acid	2-Nitro	3-Nitro	4-Nitro
0	383.14	401.48	406.06	369.86
10	298.24	301.88	315.45	336.93
20	274.32	190.74	257.42	274.30
30	201.11	184.11	186.18	226.06
40	133.45	141.45	144.61	173.15
50	107.35	91.65	131.74	114.38
60	125.22	60.91	102.46	85.53
70	130.48	29.98	96.95	97.23

The differences of conductivity values of the acids must be due to the differences in the conductivity values of the substituted anions though (except water) λ_0^- values are not known. The λ_0^- values in water at 298 K calculated from the data of Niazi *et al.* are 33.32, 51.66, 56.24 and 20.64 for benzoate, 2-, 3- and 4- nitrobenzoate ions. Except for formate ion, conductivities of monovalent organic ions like acetate *etc.* or other ions in water are usually in the range²⁹ 30–40. The values 51.66 and 56.24 appear to be high. Moreover, the limiting λ_0^+ and λ_0^- values should decrease with increase in organic co-solvent.

In absence of $\lambda_{(\text{H}^+)}^0$ values in aquo-organic mixtures, divisions of Λ_0 -values in mixed solvents are not possible. However, [$\lambda_0^-(\text{nitrobenzoate}) - \lambda_0^-(\text{benzoate})$] are given for comparison (Table 6).

The abnormally large or low (even negative) values of λ_0^- (anions) cannot be attributed to ion-solvent interactions or preferential solvation of ions.

It is obvious that Lea-Wheaton³² or Fuoss equation³³ does not give accurate values of Λ_0 , and K_a values of weak acids are likely to be erroneous. We did not use Fuoss equa-

Table 6.

Wt. % of ethanol	2-Nitro	3-Nitro	4-Nitro
10	3.6	17.2	38.7
20	-83.6	-16.9	-0.0
30	-17.0	-14.9	24.9
40	8.0	11.1	39.9
50	-15.7	24.4	7.0
60	-64.3	-22.7	-39.7
70	-101.5	-33.5	-33.2

tion³³ for the determination of the dissociation constants of the weak acids particularly in mixed solvents. The pK values of the acids increase with increase in organic solvents. The plots of pK against 1/ε or wt% of alcohol become non-linear above 40% of alcohol.

The Gibbs energy of transfer for the reaction (1) in going from water to mixed solvents, i.e. $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ can be written as

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_{t(\text{el})}^0 + \Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0 \quad (14)$$

$\Delta G_{t(\text{el})}^0$ represents the electrostatic contributions due to ion (calculated using Born equation³⁴) and should be the same for all benzoate ions as the radii of the benzoate ions are likely to be the same. The variations in $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ is obviously due to variations in non-electrostatic contributions.

In view of the uncertainties of the radii of the ions (for H⁺ ion and unsymmetrical benzoate ions), $\Delta G_{t(\text{el})}^0$ though not calculated can be taken to be equal for all benzoic acids. But the variation of non-electrostatic components due to introduction of substituents can be had from the relation,

$$\delta \Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0 = \Delta G_t^0(1) (\text{substituted acid}) - \Delta G_t^0(1) (\text{benzoic acid}) \quad (15)$$

The variation of $\Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0$ (Fig. 2) results from the changed solute-solvent interactions arising from the introduction of electron-attracting substituents in the parent compound and structural variations of the solvent mixtures. $\Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0$ values (except for 2-nitro compound) usually decrease and become minimum near about 65wt% of alcohol + water mixtures. $\Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0$ values suggest that the interactions of the halo-substituted compounds are almost similar but the interactions of 2-, 3- and 4-substituted compounds differ due to the differences in dipole moments, polarizability of the solute molecules. The results suggest that the substituents favour dissociation processes compared to the parent compounds but the solvents have a positive role in the dissociation processes.

Transfer Gibbs energy changes of electrolytes provide

Fig. 2. Plots of $\delta \Delta G_{t(\text{non-el})}^0 [= \Delta G_t^0(1)_{\text{subs.acids}} - \Delta G_t^0(1)_{\text{acids}}]$ of substituted benzoic acids vs wt% EtOH.

little idea regarding solvent effects on solute-solvent interactions. But the transfer Gibbs energy changes of single ions give relative magnitudes of the differences in the ion-solvent interactions of ions. The single ion values $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ for the acids can be calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = \Delta G_t^0(H^+) + \Delta G_t^0(A^-) - \Delta G_t^0(HA) \quad (16)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_t^0(A^-) = \Delta G_t^0(1) - \Delta G_t^0(H^+) + \Delta G_t^0(HA) \quad (17)$$

The first and the third terms on the right-hand-side of eqn. (17) were determined experimentally. $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ values were taken from the previous works³⁵. $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ values are recorded in Table 7. The accuracy of $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ depends on the accuracy of $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ values. Accuracy of single ion values is difficult to predict as the values are based on extrathermodynamic assumptions and have limitations. In spite of limitations, accuracy of the values can be taken to be within $\pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. $\Delta G_t^0(H^+)$ values reported by Wells³⁶ in water-rich binary mixtures (upto 50 wt%) have not been taken into consideration as the values actually represent the Gibbs energies of transfer of HCl rather than that of H⁺ ion from water of ionic strength 1 M to aquo-organic mixtures of ionic strength 1 M. Other limitations are also known^{37,38}.

Table 7. Gibbs energy of transfer of anion $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ of substituted-benzoic acid (in kJ mol^{-1}) in EtOH + H_2O mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% of EtOH	$\Delta G_t^0(\text{H}^+)$	Chlorobenzoic acids			Bromobenzoic acids			Iodobenzoic acids			Nitrobenzoic acids		
		2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-	2-	3-	4-
8.0	-1.08	1.26	1.36	1.72	1.00	1.02	1.40	0.95	1.19	0.82	2.45	1.32	1.12
16.4	-1.83	2.45	2.33	2.89	2.29	1.58	1.96	2.34	1.65	1.33	4.06	1.50	1.86
25.3	-2.70	4.48	2.64	3.42	4.12	1.80	2.38	4.36	2.08	1.94	6.58	3.28	2.37
34.4	-3.38	5.01	1.63	3.09	4.42	2.20	2.41	4.86	1.13	3.30	8.90	4.79	3.70
44.0	-4.52	5.70	2.01	3.81	4.92	2.33	1.90	5.18	1.50	3.78	9.46	4.82	6.26
54.1	-5.53	5.84	2.75	5.04	4.18	2.64	2.86	5.38	2.31	4.29	9.67	4.98	7.92
64.7	-5.63	6.06	3.47	4.81	5.39	3.09	2.99	5.46	2.71	4.06	10.87	5.08	8.20
76.0	-5.53	6.26	4.39	4.59	5.47	4.17	3.24	5.62	3.54	4.08	11.40	7.40	8.37
87.6	-4.66	6.35	3.95	3.13	5.59	4.29	2.86	5.86	3.19	2.32	11.86	9.17	8.57

$\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ values have been found to be predominantly positive, a fact generally observed in practice^{1,7-10}. $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ values are usually in the order 2- > 3- > 4-.

The halides behave in a similar way but NO_2 group behaves in a different way. $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ (for nitro and *ortho* compounds) increases monotonously (Fig. 3). For 3- and 4-chloro and iodo compounds, $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ values pass usually through a maxima at 76 and 54 wt%, respectively. It is expected that the stabilization of anions due to hydrogen bonding in aqueous system decreases as we go from aqueous to aquo-organic solvents with decreased H-bonding capabili-

ties and increased basicity (maximum near 65 wt% of alcohol). But it is apparent that electrostatic interactions are more predominant than non-electrostatic interactions like dipole-dipole, dipole induced dipole, dispersion interactions etc. in case of ions. The quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions can be obtained from the Gibbs energies of transfer of benzoate ions. However, the true interaction energies can be obtained from $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ if the values of the cavity and other related terms can be separately calculated.

It is well known that the scaled particle theory is applicable for hard sphere molecules and can not be utilised in case of benzoate ions. But in the absence of suitable equation it is desirable to utilise the scaled particle theory with modifications for electrically charged ions as follows³⁹.

$$\Delta G_t^0(A^-) = \Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^0(A^-) + \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(A^-) + \Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0(A^-) + RT \ln V_w/V_m \quad (18)$$

where, $\Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^0(A^-)$ is the Gibbs energy change due to cavity information, $\Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(A^-)$ the Gibbs energy change due to interaction of ions (non-electrostatic) with solvents, $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0(A^-)$ the Gibbs energy change due to electrostatic interaction, and V_w and V_m are the molar volumes of water and mixed solvents.

In view of limitations given before, no attempt has been made to calculate $\Delta G_{t,\text{cav}}^0(A^-)$ and $\Delta G_{t,\text{el}}^0(A^-)$. But the terms can be considered to be equal for all benzoate ions. Thus, one can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{ion})_{\text{subs}} &= \Delta G_t^0(A^-)_{\text{subs}} - \Delta G_t^0(A^-)_{\text{parent}} \quad (19) \\ &= \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(A^-)_{\text{subs}} - \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(A^-)_{\text{parent}} \\ &= [\Delta G_t^0(1)(\text{HA})_{\text{subs}} - \Delta G_t^0(1)(\text{HA})] + \\ &\quad [\Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})_{\text{subs}} - \Delta G_t^0(\text{HA})] \quad (20) \end{aligned}$$

i.e. the change in the interaction energies $\Delta \Delta G_{t,\text{int}}^0(\text{ion})$ due to substituents can be had from the experimentally deter-

Fig. 3. Plots of $\Delta G_t^0(A^-)$ of substituted-benzoic acids against wt% of EtOH.

measured quantities which depend only on uncertainties in experimental determinations. The plot of $\Delta G_{t,int}^0(\text{ion})$ against solvent composition (Fig. 4) gives the variation of interaction energies of ions due to substituents with variation of solvent compositions. The contrasting behaviour of $\Delta G_{t,int}^0(\text{neut})$ and $\Delta G_{t,int}^0(\text{ion})$ can be had from the comparison of Figs. 1 and 4. The variation of the interaction energies of neutral molecules and ions with the solvent composition is apparent from the curves. The complete analysis of the different interaction terms is not possible. But it is desirable to have more data for proper and better analysis on solute-solvent or ion-solvent interactions.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\Delta G_{t,int}^0(\text{ion})_{\text{subs}}$ of substituted-benzoic acids vs wt % of EtOH.

Experimental

Absolute ethanol (Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Ltd.) was treated with CaO (A.R., Glaxo) and kept overnight. The solution was filtered through non-absorbent cotton. The filtrate was distilled. The distillate was refluxed with metallic sodium for 2-3 h and finally distilled and the middle fraction was used.

Triple-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. The mixed solvents were prepared by mixing the solvents by volume and converted into weight percentage using appropriate density values of the solvents. The

dielectric constants of binary mixtures were taken from the literature⁴⁰. Substituted benzoic acids (2-, 3- and 4- chloro, bromo, iodo and nitro) were of Flukas's Puriss grade or of E. Merck's G.R. grade. The compounds were heated in an air oven at 390 K for 1 h and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The compounds were estimated volumetrically using phenolphthalein indicator. Succinic acid, potassium hydrogen phthalate, perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and potassium hydroxide used were of G.R. quality from E. Merck or B.D.H. The potassium salts of the acids were prepared by mixing known amounts of KOH with a little excess of the acids. The salts were washed with ether to remove excess acids and crystallised from aqueous alcohol (10 : 90, v/v%) mixtures, recrystallised from alcohol, dried and kept in a vacuum desiccator.

The solubility measurements were made using Campbell solubility apparatus⁴¹ in the way described in our previous publications⁷⁻¹⁰.

Conductance was measured with a Kyoto Electronics GM-115 conductance bridge (Japan) using a specially designed Kyoto conductivity cell; cell constant (1.009 cm^{-1}) was determined using KCl solutions as described by Jones and Bradshaw⁴². For the determination of the dissociation constants, conductances of the acid solutions (usually of the order of 2×10^{-3} to $9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) were measured. The measurements were made at $298 \pm 0.2 \text{ K}$. Data for HClO_4 and KClO_4 were utilised from our previous works.

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